

ETHNOPSYCHOLOGY AND ITS SUBJECT AND METHODS

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Abstract. This article talks about ethnopsychology and its subject, methods, ethnopsychological research.

Key words: ethnopsychology, ethnology, psychology, ethnos, methods issue.

ЭТНОПСИХОЛОГИЯ И ЕЕ ПРЕДМЕТ И МЕТОДЫ

Аннотация. В статье говорится об этнопсихологии и ее предмете, методах, этнопсихологических исследованиях.

Ключевые слова: этнопсихология, этнология, психология, этнос, проблема методов.

Ethnopsychology is such a branch of psychology that, in addition to the psychology of certain nationalities, it also studies the psychology of different peoples and small national groups. The term "ethnopsychology" is a combination of the concepts of "ethnology" and "psychology", and the Greek word "ethnos" means people, tribe, and "psychology" means the science of the soul. This science studies the unique mental image, behavior, "mentality" of the representatives of a certain nation and ethnic group.

The emergence, manifestation, and transformation of national character, customs and traditions, national feelings and taste (taab), ethnic consciousness and national self-awareness characteristic of each nation. and issues such as development are also the subject of study of ethnopsychology. In turn, it is worth noting that ethnopsychology, in turn, is an applied direction of social psychology. One of the branches of science close to ethnopsychology is ethnography, which compares and compares the characteristics of certain cultures. In this sense, ethnopsychology is a branch of science that studies complex relationships in groups of people belonging to different ethnic groups and specializes in their regulation.

Social psychology, which studies the influence of such and other public psychological processes on the social behavior of an individual, and ethnopsychology, which is its special branch, have great practical importance in knowing social-psychological laws and managing them. The emergence, manifestation, change of national character, customs and traditions, national feelings

and taste (taab), ethnic consciousness and national self-awareness characteristic of each nation. and issues such as development are also an object of study of ethnopsychology.

It raises the issue of representative, reliable methods in ethnopsychological research. Each researcher who aims to deal with the problem of ethnopsychology is forced to either change one of the existing methods or, if not, to discover a new method on his own. Finally, the inconvenience of using ethnopsychological methods is that, for example, the methodology that gave very good results in America and allowed to collect reliable data may not measure or determine anything at all in the conditions of Asian countries or our republic. For example, Raven's matrix test and Cattell's intelligence test, which are considered to be unaffected by environmental influences, still require environmental conditions to be taken into account, albeit partially. In addition, their interpretation and data analysis require special care and intelligence. That's why scientists from all over the world now share a common opinion about the groundlessness of the idea of creating a universal test or methodology that is above any cultural environment.

Any researcher who aims to conduct ethnopsychological research should take into account the diversity of the cultural environment and their mutual influence as the main principles. This must be taken into account when creating an ethnopsychological research program. For example, if you want to conduct research in the conditions of Uzbekistan, you should pay attention to the following things: 1) common psychological factors characteristic of different nationalities living in the conditions of this region and methods of their identification; 2) to identify psychological qualities and factors unique to the Uzbek nation; 3) selection of methods that allow to measure or experimentally check identified factors or psychological qualities and adapt them to concrete conditions; 4) providing the research team with employees who know the language and customs of the national group under investigation.

Because it is necessary to conduct research in the language of the group that is considered the object of research, so that every request, question and task put to the examinees is understandable for them. It should be noted that there are no special methods aimed at checking the psychology of this or that national group, its ethnic stereotypes, therefore, the researches are selected and sorted from among the available methods. At the next stage, the selected methods will be adapted to the local conditions of the inspection, and if necessary, it will be necessary to translate them from one language to another.

For example, when conducting research in Karakalpakstan, it must be taken into account that each methodology should be in at least three languages: Uzbek, Karakalpak and, if necessary, in Russian. Regarding the translation, it should be said that the translation of special psychological tests or methods (questionnaires, questionnaires, scale questions) requires high knowledge and professional qualities from the translator. Otherwise, the methodology may lose its value or may not identify or measure the desired quality. Even using non-verbal tests in different conditions, it has been proven in many studies that its content or purpose has changed at the stage of interpreting the obtained data. Therefore, before using any methodological method, it is advisable to test it in a small group and check the results by giving them to experts or retesting them using other auxiliary methods.

Another requirement for concrete ethnopsychological research is to conduct the research in natural conditions, in places familiar to the investigators, with brief instructions. Because people of different ages, professions, and education often participate in ethnopsychological research, the number of participants means many, sometimes thousands of respondents, unlike investigations conducted in ordinary laboratory conditions. That's why being able to create a system of clear, clear assignments for all of them requires a number of professional skills from a psychologist.

In our opinion, the most important among the ethnopsychological problems at the moment is the study of ethnic stereotypes among representatives of one or another nationality. What methods can be used for this? According to the Russian researcher G. U. Ksoyeva, four groups of methods can be indicated here:

1. Scale measurement methods - they mainly check different ethnic ustanovkas in the representatives of the nation. For example, the famous scale of Bogardus: pairs given by means of comparative reasoning is based on an accurate evaluation by each examinee. Or, Likert's "sum of evaluations" method also determines the examinee's objection or recognition to the opinion of a representative of this or that nation. We can say that these methods have been used in many studies worldwide and set a record in terms of adaptation to local conditions.

2. Methods of observation and questioning - in this, the material and spiritual values, household conditions, customs, traditions, and hakazos, which are characteristic of that cultural environment and are considered its inestimable wealth, are studied from the outside. Among the methods of questioning, the questionnaire method is mostly used, in which the lifestyle and autobiographical information of

the representative of the nation is determined, and scientific conclusions are content-analyzed.

American scientists Katz and Braley used a unique form of the questioning method to identify ethnic stereotypes. For example, they gave a list of as many answers as possible to the subject of interest and asked him to select "his" from among these answers. In addition, from the list containing 84 different qualities, they were given the task of distinguishing 5 leading qualities characteristic of their own nation and of another nation. In this way, ethnic stereotypes were determined.

3. Projective methods - this group of methods used in ethnopsychological research mainly includes Rorschach's "ink blot" test, thematic apperception test (TAT), sentence completion test, photo evaluation test, Lovenfeld's mosaic test, and others.

Stereotypes of different nationalities were also studied in terms of the quality of the performance of abstract tasks and the direction of the answers.

4. Tests aimed at determining individual qualities of a person. For example, tests aimed at studying national character traits by G. Deyker and N. Freud. They mainly study the impressionability and emotional reactions of a person. In addition, this group of tests includes a special intelligence test, a study of the spiritual outlook, a sense of justice, tests of artistic taste and other tests. Studying the language of the nation with all linguistic methods, especially when determining national stereotypes, also allows to collect very valuable information.

Because the language plays the role of the main tool in the assimilation of the national values and stereotypes of the representative of this or that nation. That is why ethnopsychological research is carried out in collaboration with linguists, ethnographers, ethnologists, sociologists, and historians. First of all, the researcher must have the ability to know the language of the people in the environment he is investigating, the "language" through the language. Therefore, a person who aims to study the national character, traditions, and values should first of all know the language of this people and nation perfectly. The aforementioned methodological and methodical methods are only the main ones in the study of national psychology.

Because many more methods can be used to study the psychological state of many aspects of the nation, which depends on the goals of the research and the level of methodological training of the researcher. In any case, in recent years, in a number of scientific and research works conducted in Uzbekistan, first of all, special attention is paid to the use of methodologies that are suitable for our national and cultural environment, and to adapt the methodologies developed by foreigners to our

national environment. In this case, the same test or methodological method is used on several thousand respondents, the obtained results are studied with the help of experts from the point of view of validity with the data obtained using another method, the results are compared, and only then they are presented to large audiences. It is allowed to interpret the results. This means compliance with ethical norms in the application of socio-psychological methods.

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